

Observation of quantum-correlated twin beams in cascaded nonlinear interactions

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We report on the generation of twin beams through a cascaded process of optical parametric oscillation in a doubly resonant second-harmonic generation system. These bright beams exhibit strong quantum correlations, enabling the observation of up to 5 dB of noise reduction in their intensity difference below the standard quantum limit.

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Squeezed states of light are a key resource for the implementation of several quantum communication and computation protocols with continuous variables [1,2], the demonstration of teleportation and the Einstein–Podolsky–Rosen paradox [3–5], and the improvement of the precision of measurements beyond the shot noise limit (SNL) [6,7]. In a squeezed state of light, the uncertainty in a field observable is reduced below the shot noise limit (SNL) at the cost of increased uncertainty in the conjugate observable, in accordance with the Heisenberg uncertainty principle. In particular, twin beams (TBs), such as those generated by parametric downconversion, exhibit strong intensity correlation, which results in squeezing of the intensity difference observable, as first reported by Heidmann *et al.* [8]. In addition, phase quadratures are correspondingly anti-correlated, which leads to squeezing of the phase sum observable and to entanglement between the two fields [9]. TBs have been originally generated by means of parametric downconversion in $\chi^{(2)}$ media [8,10–12] and subsequently through four-wave mixing in third-order nonlinear media [13,14] and atomic systems [15–17]. Applications of quantum properties of TBs have been devised and partially demonstrated for quantum key distribution protocols [18], quantum generation of random numbers [19], quantum imaging [20–22], and spectroscopy [23,24].

Here we report on the observation of intensity difference squeezing in TBs generated in a resonator where cascaded $\chi^{(2)}$ nonlinear processes occur. In particular, a primary process of intracavity second-harmonic generation (SHG) of the pump laser is followed by a cascaded, internally pumped optical parametric oscillation (OPO), which generates two parametric

modes around the pump frequency, with striking analogy to four-wave mixing in a Kerr medium. In fact, this system is far richer in its dynamics: for instance, a multiplicity of cascaded three-wave interactions may occur, leading to the formation of multimode comb patterns [25].

Whenever the first two nonlinear processes are considered (SHG and OPO), only four modes are present in the stationary regime of the nonlinear cavity: the fundamental frequency, its second harmonic, and the TBs. In this configuration, their interplay is predicted to produce excellent noise suppression in the intensity difference of the two downconverted modes, as it occurs for TBs in a direct OPO. Also, novel nonclassical phenomena can be produced, i.e., the intensity sum of the two beams is also squeezed, and the squeezing in the second-harmonic quadratures can be spectrally tuned with the pumping power [26–28]. Finally, quadripartite entanglement has been predicted to occur among the fundamental, second-harmonic, and TB modes [29]. Nevertheless, scarce experimental attention has been paid to the detection of quantum properties of the four interacting modes, except for the effect of parametric fields on the squeezing of the fundamental and second-harmonic fields [30].

In this work, we operate the nonlinear cavity in the specific configuration described above, characterized by the interaction of SHG and nondegenerate downconversion, and focus on the quantum correlation in the intensity difference of the TBs. The power spectral density of the intensity difference, normalized to its corresponding shot noise level, reads as [27]

$$S(\nu) = 1 - \frac{\xi \eta_d}{1 + (\nu/\gamma)^2}, \quad (1)$$

where ν is the spectral frequency, γ is the cavity linewidth (HWHM) for the subharmonic frequency, η_d is the detection quantum efficiency, and $\xi = T/(T + L)$ is the cavity escape efficiency (T is the transmission coefficient of the coupling mirror and L is the extra cavity loss coefficient). The noise reduction is proportional to both η_d and ξ in a frequency bandwidth set by the cavity linewidth. Interestingly, the noise reduction expressed in formula (1) coincides with that of a direct OPO [10,31].

Figure 1 shows a scheme of our experiment: a cw Nd:YAG laser at 1064.45 nm is used to pump a periodically poled lithium

Fig. 1. Scheme of the four-mirror, traveling-wave cavity for twin-beams generation with balanced system for squeezing detection. PPLN, periodically poled lithium niobate crystal; PD, photodiode; EOM, electro-optic modulator; DM, dichroic mirror; PZT, piezoelectric actuator.

niobate nonlinear crystal, placed inside a cavity resonant for both the fundamental and second-harmonic frequencies [32].

All cavity mirrors are high reflection coated ($R > 99.9\%$ at both 1064 and 532 nm), except for a partial reflective coupling mirror ($R = 91.5\%$ at 1064 nm, $R = 96.0\%$ at 532 nm). The measured cavity-free spectral range is 504 MHz, with a cold cavity resonance full width at half maximum of 8.4 MHz and a finesse of 60. The high-reflectivity plane mirror is mounted on a piezoelectric actuator (PZT) for cavity length control. The double resonance condition is achieved by means of an angle-adjustable, 3-mm-thick silica window inside the cavity, which compensates for the effect of different refractive index values on the optical path at the fundamental frequency and second harmonic. Phase matching for the generation of the second harmonic of the fundamental wavelength is achieved by active stabilization of the crystal temperature. The same condition guarantees phase matching for the inverse process of nearly degenerate parametric oscillation: when the input power exceeds a definite threshold, a cascaded process of parametric oscillation starts to be pumped by the generated second harmonic, giving rise to two sidebands around the fundamental frequency.

This system shows different regimes for the generation of TBs, which are characterized by the spectral distance of the sidebands from the pump wavelength. Such regimes are accessible through a Pound–Drever–Hall offset locking technique, which permits to arbitrarily adjust the frequency detuning between the laser and the cavity resonance over a wide spectral range by acting on the cavity length. For our measurements, we identified at least two stable regimes of interest: TBs are generated at ± 21.0 nm and ± 2.4 nm from the pump wavelength.

In order to observe squeezing, the TBs exit the cavity through the output coupler, collinearly with the fundamental and second-harmonic beams, and are spatially separated through a diffraction grating (600 grooves/mm, with an efficiency of 87%), while the residual second harmonic is successively filtered by a dichroic mirror. After blocking the fundamental beam, the TBs are analyzed by a balanced detection system, consisting of a pair of identical InGaAs photodiodes (ETX500), with a measured quantum efficiency of 78%, followed by well-matched homemade low-noise amplifiers, for a final common mode rejection ratio of >30 dB and a detection bandwidth of 20 MHz. The DC part of the photocurrents is used as a monitor and for shot noise calibration, while the AC signal provides information on

Fig. 2. Noise spectrum of the photocurrents difference for TBs at ± 21 nm, normalized to the shot noise level (dashed line). A residual amplitude noise partially masks the squeezing curve. For visualization purposes, the spectrum shown is a 25 point average of the original data. The inset shows the amplitude noise spectrum of the laser source in the 0–20 MHz range, with a peak around 2 MHz.

nonclassical properties of the TBs. In particular, the AC signals from the photodiodes are subtracted, low-pass-filtered, and amplified, the resulting signal being proportional to the noise in the intensity difference. This time trace is acquired by an oscilloscope and Fourier-transformed to obtain the power spectral density. We averaged over 50 acquisitions of the power spectra, with a resolution bandwidth of 7.63 kHz.

Our first observation was realized by injecting in the cavity 200 mW of fundamental power and locking the cavity to it with a finite detuning with respect to the central frequency. We generated TBs at ± 21 nm from the pump wavelength of 1064.45 nm, with 12 mW of power in each sideband.

Figure 2 shows the power spectral density of the intensity difference noise, normalized to the corresponding photodiodes' shot noise level. Fluctuations in the intensity difference are below the shot noise in the frequency bandwidth up to about 13 MHz, demonstrating the presence of quantum correlations. We also note a residual amplitude noise, partially masking the squeezing curve in the frequency range from 1 to 5 MHz, due to a slight residual unbalance in the intensities of the TBs: this condition makes the squeezing measurements trickier. Such an unbalance is not an intrinsic feature of the TB generation process at these wavelengths; rather, we guess it is a consequence of the nonconstant spectral response of the cavity's optics over wide spectral spans. The noise reduction reaches a minimum of -2.0 ± 0.4 dB around 800 kHz, which, corrected for the total quantum efficiency $\eta_d = (66 \pm 1)\%$, results in -3.6 ± 0.9 dB of generated squeezing at the cavity exit. The clearance of shot-to-dark noise for this measurement is 16 dB.

In a second set of measurements, we changed the laser-to-cavity detuning in order to generate TBs at ± 2.4 nm from the pump. Interestingly, this emission regime was characterized by a relatively higher nonlinear conversion efficiency: despite lower fundamental power, we generated more powerful sidebands. We replaced the diffraction grating to obtain a higher dispersive power: we thus enhanced the diffraction efficiency (1200 grooves/mm) at the expense of a lower grating efficiency (78%).

Fig. 3. Normalized noise spectra of the photocurrents difference for TBs at ± 2.4 nm, for three different pump powers. For visualization purposes, the spectra shown are 25 points averages of the original data.

The total quantum efficiency for this measurement results in $\eta_d = (60 \pm 1)\%$.

We performed correlation measurements with three different pumping powers, i.e., 50, 100, and 150 mW, generating 4, 12, and 21 mW of power in each TB, respectively. These observations permitted us to verify the independence of the squeezing level from the pump power, in agreement with (1). This level reaches a minimum of -2.3 ± 0.3 dB around 900 kHz, which, corrected for the losses along the detection branch, results in -5.0 ± 1.3 dB of generated squeezing at the cavity exit. For this set of measurements, the lowest clearance of shot-to-dark noise is 10 dB, corresponding to 4 mW of TBs' power. The results are shown in Fig. 3.

In the same generation regime of our system, we finally introduced a tunable loss on the TBs' power, in order to verify the linear dependence of the squeezing level from power losses. It is known that power losses degrade the squeezing level according to [33]

$$S_\epsilon(\nu) = (1 - \epsilon)S(\nu) + \epsilon, \quad (2)$$

where $S_\epsilon(\nu)$ is the normalized power spectral density of the intensity difference after loss, ϵ is the attenuation factor, and $S(\nu)$ is the normalized power spectral density in (1). The variable loss was realized by introducing a half-wave plate and a polarizing beam splitter on the TBs' path before the diffraction grating. The cavity was pumped with 50 mW of the fundamental frequency power, and the total power in each TB before attenuation was 4 mW. The results are shown in Fig. 4.

In conclusion, we realized quantum-correlated twin beams via internally pumped optical parametric oscillation in a doubly resonant second-harmonic cavity and observed a noise reduction up to 5 dB in their intensity difference. To our knowledge, this is the first experimental observation of squeezing in twin beams generated through cascaded quadratically nonlinear processes in a single cavity. The demonstration of twin-beam correlations in our cascaded system opens the way to extensive investigations of its exclusive nonclassical properties. In fact, the complex interactions between SHG and OPO lead to a variety of nonclassical effects that are not accessible via each single nonlinear process, such as multipartite entanglement, which is of paramount

Fig. 4. Spectral variance of the intensity difference at a sideband frequency of 4 MHz as a function of the attenuation of TBs. The points are the experimental data on a linear scale normalized to the corresponding shot noise level. The solid line is a linear fit.

importance for the development of advanced quantum communication protocols [34]. Further investigations of these properties in systems based on cascaded quadratic processes could help in establishing more compact and stable schemes, such as nonlinear microresonators [35,36], as viable and efficient sources of nonclassical light.

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Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

1. S. Lloyd and S. L. Braunstein, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **82**, 1784 (1999).
2. S. L. Braunstein and P. van Loock, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **77**, 513 (2005).
3. Z. Y. Ou, S. F. Pereira, H. J. Kimble, *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **68**, 3663 (1992).
4. N. Takei, T. Aoki, S. Koike, *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. A* **72**, 042304 (2005).
5. H. Yonezawa, S. L. Braunstein, and A. Furusawa, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **99**, 110503 (2007).
6. J. Aasi, J. Abadie, B. P. Abbott, *et al.*, *Nat. Photonics* **7**, 613 (2013).
7. B. J. Lawrie, P. D. Lett, A. M. Marino, *et al.*, *ACS Photonics* **6**, 1307 (2019).
8. A. Heidmann, R. Horowicz, S. Reynaud, *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **59**, 2555 (1987).
9. A. S. Villar, L. S. Cruz, K. N. Cassemiro, *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **95**, 243603 (2005).
10. J. Mertz, T. Debuisschert, A. Heidmann, *et al.*, *Opt. Lett.* **16**, 1234 (1991).
11. J. G. Rarity, P. R. Tapster, J. A. Levenson, *et al.*, *Appl. Phys. B* **55**, 250 (1992).
12. J. Teja and N. C. Wong, *Opt. Express* **2**, 65 (1998).

13. A. Dutt, K. Luke, S. Manipatruni, *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Appl.* **3**, 044005 (2015).
14. V. D. Vaidya, B. Morrison, L. G. Helt, *et al.*, *Sci. Adv.* **6**, eaba9186 (2020).
15. C. F. McCormick, V. Boyer, E. Arimondo, *et al.*, *Opt. Lett.* **32**, 178 (2007).
16. M. Guo, H. Zhou, D. Wang, *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. A* **89**, 033813 (2014).
17. B. L. Schmittberger, K. M. Jones, M.-C. Wu, *et al.*, *Opt. Express* **27**, 4769 (2019).
18. C. Silberhorn, N. Korolkova, and G. Leuchs, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **88**, 167902 (2002).
19. Q. Zhang, X. Deng, C. Tian, *et al.*, *Opt. Lett.* **42**, 895 (2017).
20. V. Boyer, A. M. Marino, and P. D. Lett, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **100**, 143601 (2008).
21. V. Boyer, A. M. Marino, R. C. Pooser, *et al.*, *Science* **321**, 544 (2008).
22. G. Brida, M. Genovese, A. Meda, *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. A* **83**, 033811 (2011).
23. P. H. S. Ribeiro, C. Schwob, A. Maitre, *et al.*, *Opt. Lett.* **22**, 1893 (1997).
24. H. Wang, Z. Zhai, S. Wang, *et al.*, *Europhys. Lett.* **64**, 15 (2003).
25. I. Ricciardi, S. Mosca, M. Parisi, *et al.*, *Micromachines* **11**, 230 (2020).
26. M. A. M. Marte, *Acta Phys. Slovaca* **45**, 253 (1995).
27. M. A. M. Marte, *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* **12**, 2296 (1995).
28. S. Schiller, R. Bruckmeier, and A. G. White, *Opt. Commun.* **138**, 158 (1997).
29. H.-T. Tan and H. Huang, *Phys. Rev. A* **83**, 015802 (2011).
30. A. G. White, "Classical and quantum dynamics of optical frequency conversion," Ph.D. thesis, (Australian National University, 1997).
31. C. Fabre, E. Giacobino, A. Heidmann, *et al.*, *J. Phys.* **50**, 1209 (1989).
32. I. Ricciardi, P. Maddaloni, P. De Natale, *et al.*, *Opt. Express* **30**, 45694 (2022).
33. H.-A. Bachor and T. C. Ralph, *A Guide to Experiments in Quantum Optics*, 2nd ed. (Wiley-VCH, 2009).
34. A. S. Coelho, F. A. S. Barbosa, K. N. Cassemiro, *et al.*, *Science* **326**, 823 (2009).
35. J. Szabados, D. N. Puzyrev, Y. Minet, *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **124**, 203902 (2020).
36. I. Hendry, L. S. Trainor, Y. Xu, *et al.*, *Opt. Lett.* **45**, 1204 (2020).